

Signal Growth in a Pure Time-Modulated Transmission Line and the Loss Effect: supplemental document

This supplemental document mainly discusses solving the eigenvalue problem and plotting the dispersion diagram in a transmission line with a time-modulated Bloch impedance. Three models are investigated: a lossless L-C TL lumped model loaded with a shunt lossless TMC and a TL loaded with a shunt lossless and lossy TMC. Using the way discussed in this supplemental document, all dispersion diagrams could be plotted in the main manuscript.

1. DISPERSION EQUATION OF A LOSSLESS TL LUMPED MODEL WITH TIME-MODULATED CAPACITOR

This section constructs the dispersion equation of a lossless lumped model TL loaded with a time-modulated capacitor. The unit cell of the loaded TL is shown in Fig. S1(a), which is a T-shape symmetric unit cell constructed from two different elements, series, and shunt. The shunt element (B) will always be the time-modulated capacitor, while The series element (A) will be a time-invariant inductor.

A. Transfer matrix of time-modulated capacitor

To construct the dispersion equation, transfer matrices of all elements are computed. As in [1–4], a time-modulated capacitor with a period T that follows the function $C(\omega, t) = C(\omega, t + nT)$ with $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ can be expanded into a complex Fourier series as follows

$$C(\omega, t) = \sum_{s=-\infty}^{+\infty} c_s(\omega) e^{js\omega_M t} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $c_s(\omega)$ are complex coefficients and ω_M is the angular modulation frequency. When the time-modulated capacitor is connected to a circuit operating at angular signal frequency ω_s , an infinite number of Floquet harmonics are generated; the voltage or current across the time-modulated capacitor follows the series below [2]

$$F(t) = \sum_{n=-N}^{+N} f_n e^{j\omega_n t} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where f_n are the complex coefficients of voltage and current. N is an integer that represents half the number of considered harmonics in the problem and depends on the electrical size of the unit cell. According to [2], it can be approximated by

$$N \ll \frac{\lambda_s}{d} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where λ_s is the signal's wavelength, and d is the length of the unit cell. The harmonic frequencies can be given by

$$\omega_n = \omega_s + n\omega_M \quad (\text{S4})$$

where ω_s and ω_M are the main signal and modulation angular frequencies, respectively. Eq. S1 depends mainly on the modulation waveform. In this manuscript, the capacitance is modulated around its nominal value in a sinusoidal manner following

$$C(\omega, t) = C_o(\omega) (1 + M_D \cos(\omega_M t + \varphi_M)) \quad (\text{S5})$$

where M_D and φ_M are the modulation depth and phase, respectively. $C_o(\omega)$ is the capacitance nominal value. Using (S5), (S1) is reduced to

$$C(\omega, t) = C_o(\omega) + C_{-1}(\omega) e^{-j\omega_M t} + C_1(\omega) e^{j\omega_M t} \quad (\text{S6})$$

Fig. S1. (a) General symmetric unit cell of an ideal transmission line. Series element (A) and shunt element (B) considering (b) a unit cell of a lossless lumped model of a transmission line with a time-modulated capacitor, a unit cell of a lossless TL with a length of $m\lambda_m$ and 90Ω characteristic impedance loaded with (c) lossless time-modulated capacitor, (d) lossy time-modulated capacitor.

where $C_{\pm 1}(\omega) = 0.5 C_0(\omega) M_D e^{\pm j\varphi_M}$.

In general, as discussed in [2, 3, 5], the time-modulated capacitor generated current and voltage harmonics are related by

$$i_l = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} j \omega_r c_{l-n}(\omega_l) v_n \quad (\text{S7})$$

Consequently, the admittance matrix of the time-modulated capacitor is given by

$$\bar{Y}_C = j \bar{W} P \quad (\text{S8})$$

where $\bar{W} = \text{diag}(\omega_{-N}, \dots, \omega_{-1}, \omega_s, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_N)$, and P in general is given by

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} c_0(\omega_{-N}) & c_{-1}(\omega_{1-N}) & \dots & c_{-2N}(\omega_N) \\ c_1(\omega_{-N}) & c_0(\omega_{1-N}) & & c_{1-2N}(\omega_N) \\ & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{2N}(\omega_{-N}) & c_{2N-1}(\omega_{1-N}) & \dots & c_0(\omega_N) \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S9})$$

P is $(2N+1) \times (2N+1)$ in size. Using a time-modulated capacitor that follows (S6), the P matrix is reduced to

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} c_0(\omega_{-N}) & c_{-1}(\omega_{1-N}) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ c_1(\omega_{-N}) & c_0(\omega_{1-N}) & c_{-1}(\omega_{2-N}) & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & c_1(\omega_{1-N}) & c_0(\omega_{2-N}) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & c_0(\omega_N) \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S10})$$

According to [6], the transfer matrix of a shunt time-modulated capacitor can be obtained as

$$\bar{T}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{I} & \text{Zeros} \\ \bar{Y}_C & \bar{I} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{S11})$$

where \bar{I} and Zeros are the identity and zero matrices, respectively. They have the same size of \bar{Y}_C . This makes the transfer matrix T_C of size $(4N+2) \times (4N+2)$.

B. Dispersion equation

In this section, the series element (A) in Fig. S1(a) is a time-invariant inductor. The impedance matrix of such an inductor in a time-invariant system is given by

$$\bar{Z}_L = j\bar{W}(L/2) \quad (\text{S12})$$

where $L = \bar{I} \times l_o$, and l_o is the value of the inductance. The transfer matrix of a time-invariant inductor can be obtained by

$$\bar{T}_L = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{I} & \bar{Z}_L \\ \text{Zeros} & \bar{I} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{S13})$$

The total transfer matrix of the unit cell can be obtained using

$$\bar{T}_t = \bar{T}_L \bar{T}_C \bar{T}_L \quad (\text{S14})$$

The dispersion diagram can be plotted by first solving

$$\bar{T}_t X = \bar{q} X \quad (\text{S15})$$

where X and q are the eigenvectors and values, respectively. Once the eigenvalues are obtained, the dispersion diagram is plotted using

$$q = e^{-\gamma d} \quad (\text{S16a})$$

$$\beta d = \text{real}[j \ln(q)] \quad (\text{S16b})$$

$$\alpha d = \text{real}[-\ln(q)] \quad (\text{S16c})$$

where γ is the propagation constant, β is the phase constant, α is the attenuation constant, and d is the length of the unit cell. Using (S16,S15), plotting the dispersion variation against frequency results in $(4N + 2)$ curves; two for each harmonic plus two for the fundamental frequency. This describes each frequency's forward and backward propagation defined in (S4).

A complex dispersion diagram (complex frequencies associated with fundamental ω_s and the harmonic ω_{-1}) can be plotted using the following equation instead of (S4) in solving the eigenvalue problem.

$$\Omega = \omega_n - j\sigma_n \quad (\text{S17})$$

2. SIGNAL AMPLIFICATION IN A LOSSLESS TL LOADED WITH TIME MODULATED CAPACITOR

In this section, the element (A) in Fig. S1(a) is replaced by a TL section with an electrical length of $2m\pi$ radian at the modulation frequency and 90Ω characteristic impedance (Z_o). Two conditions are considered for element (B) in Fig. S1(a): lossless time-modulated capacitor and lossy time-modulated capacitor.

A. Lossless time modulated capacitor

In this subsection, element (B) will be a lossless time-modulated capacitor. The considered series and shunt elements can be seen in Fig. S1(c), and different cases are investigated at various values of m . In order to plot the dispersion diagram, (S15) and (S16) are solved with the matrix T_L in (S14) replaced by

$$\bar{T}_{tl} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A} & \bar{B} \\ \bar{C} & \bar{D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{S18})$$

where

$$\bar{A} = \cos(2 \times \pi \times m \times \frac{\bar{W}}{\omega_M}) \quad (S19a)$$

$$\bar{B} = j \times Z_o \times \sin(2 \times \pi \times m \times \frac{\bar{W}}{\omega_M}) \quad (S19b)$$

$$\bar{C} = j \times Y_o \times \sin(2 \times \pi \times m \times \frac{\bar{W}}{\omega_M}) \quad (S19c)$$

$$\bar{D} = \cos(2 \times \pi \times m \times \frac{\bar{W}}{\omega_M}) \quad (S19d)$$

B. Lossy time modulated capacitor

In this subsection, element (B) will be a time-modulated capacitor with series resistance R_c , as illustrated in Fig. S1(d). The introduced resistance R_c adds loss to the time-modulated capacitor, and the unit cell will be studied at different R_c values. To plot the dispersion diagram, the transfer matrix of the shunt element (B) should be computed. The resistance matrix is given by

$$\bar{Z}_{Rc} = R_c \bar{I} \quad (S20)$$

where R_c is the value of the resistance. The impedance matrix of the shunt branch (B) can be calculated using

$$\bar{Z}_B = \bar{Z}_{Rc} + \bar{Y}_C^{-1} \quad (S21)$$

where \bar{Y}_C is given in (S8). The transfer matrix of shunt branch B is given by

$$\bar{T}_B = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{I} & Z_{eros} \\ \bar{Z}_B^{-1} & \bar{I} \end{bmatrix} \quad (S22)$$

The total transfer matrix of the unit cell shown in Fig. S1(d) can be obtained using

$$\bar{T}_{Rc} = \bar{T}_{tl} \bar{T}_B \bar{T}_{tl} \quad (S23)$$

3. CHOOSING THE NUMBER OF CONSIDERED HARMONICS N

Choosing the correct number of considered harmonics N is discussed in S3. To check the feasibility of S3, for a unit cell that has an absolute electrical length of 0.81 radians, $\frac{\lambda_s}{d}$ gives 7.75. So, choosing $N=3$ satisfies S3. On the other hand, it can be seen in Fig. 2(a) in the main manuscript that harmonics $\omega_{\pm 3}$ do not play any role at $F_s = 0.5$ GHz. A frequency bandgap occurs for these harmonics within the 0-1 GHz frequency range. By choosing $N=2$, the same dispersion diagram of Fig. 2 can be obtained. As a result, the correct value of N must satisfy S3, and it is also the lowest value above which the dispersion diagram no longer changes within the frequency band of interest. Moreover, solutions of eigenvalue problems do not come in order. This makes relating each curve to its corresponding harmonic tricky. Consequently, reducing the number of considered harmonics (N) to the lowest possible value decreases the complexity of the dispersion diagram and helps to identify the harmonics' curves. However, six harmonics ($N=3$) are considered in the whole manuscript to account for any changes in the dispersion diagram when the unit cell becomes more complex.

4. CODE/SOFTWARE

The reader can find the Codes and software in the following Temp. URL: (<https://datadryad.org/stash/share/a7PSkEdSZq9YsafjtCCkeuYRZHZsZZvHkPTdaxnDEbk>) at Zenodo. The project directory is organized into two main folders, MATLAB Codes and Simulator File.

A. MATLAB Codes

This folder contains all the MATLAB scripts for the proposed models, which are used to plot real and complex frequency dispersion, as well as loss dispersion. Each folder contains the eigenshuffle.m script, which arranges the eigenvalues resulting from the solution of the eigenvalue problem.

A.1. lumped model (Section 2(a))

L_C_Beta.m: Plots the real dispersion for the modulated TL lumped model. L_C_imagfre.m: Plots the complex dispersion for the modulated TL lumped model.

A.2. Lossless and lossy TL (Section 2(b))

TL_RC_Beta.m: Plots the real dispersion for the modulated TL loaded with a shunt capacitor (lossy or lossless, depending on the value of R_c). TL_RC_imagfre.m: Plots the complex dispersion for the modulated TL loaded with a shunt capacitor (lossy or lossless, depending on the value of R_c). TL_RC_ALFA.m: Plots the loss dispersion for the modulated TL loaded with a shunt capacitor (lossy or lossless, depending on the value of R_c).

B. Simulator File

This folder includes the Advanced Design System (ADS) files that validate the results obtained from the dispersion plots.

REFERENCES

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